

Allergen coverage in laboratory conditions Nasal Food Challenge (NFC)

1. First stage: for testing allergens from food forms to freeze-dried products

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Photo 1. Methods/pure lyophilized product without filtration

Eggs were purchased in the ecological local supermarket

Egg white (24.3 g) and yolk (24.9 g) from one egg were separated and freeze-dried (Christ LCG Lyo Chamber Guard, Alpha 2-4 LSC plus, Martin Christ Gefriertrocknungsanlagen GmbH, Germany)

The weights of freeze-dried powders of egg white and yolk were 4.0 g and 6.9 g, respectively

2. Second stage: titration challenge test (NFC)

*Nasal Lavage Fluid (material collected at positive NFC); VAS-Visual Analogy Scale; OR-Optical Rhinometry;

Figure 1. The study design NFC